

THERMOGRAPHIC ANALYSIS OF THE EFFECTS OF PLASMA JET ON BIOLOGICAL TISSUE

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Abstract— The atmospheric pressure plasma jet (APPJ) has gained prominence due to its versatility, operating with a reduced electric field and generating abundant reactive oxygen and nitrogen species. Its simple structure, which does not require vacuum systems, allows its use in open environments, significantly expanding its utility in fields such as sterilization, surface modification, and biomedical applications. This study aimed to evaluate the direct thermal effects caused by plasma contact with *ex vivo* biological tissue, analyzed through thermographic images. The temperature variation was assessed as a function of the type of tip used in a portable plasma device (Plasmax – KLD), equipped with two distinct fulguration tips (conical and needle holder). Plasma was applied to porcine tissue samples, and surface temperature was recorded using a FLIR T540 thermal camera. The images were analyzed with dedicated software, considering minimum, average, and maximum temperature metrics. Results revealed that the needle holder tip exhibited a more uniform thermal behavior, with lower standard deviations, indicating greater control over the applied thermal energy. In contrast, the conical tip showed greater temperature variation and higher maximum values, indicating broader thermal energy dispersion. The observed differences suggest that the geometry of the tip directly influences the thermal profile generated, which may impact the effectiveness and safety of clinical applications with potential biological effects. Tip selection should consider the thermal alteration required according to the treatment type.

Keywords— Plasma jet, infrared thermography, *ex vivo* biological tissue, biological effects.

I. INTRODUCTION

The atmospheric pressure plasma jet (APPJ) offers several advantages, making it versatile and efficient. It generates a low electric field and produces a high concentration of reactive oxygen species (ROS) and reactive nitrogen species (RNS), particularly O_2^- , OH, O_3 , H_2O_2 , NO, and NO_2 [1][2]. Moreover, its simple structure eliminates the need for a vacuum system, allowing its use in open environments and expanding its range of

applications [3]. These characteristics have led to the widespread use of APPJ in various fields, including sterilization, surface treatments (such as coating, cleaning, polymerization, and oxidation), as well as in biomedical applications and scientific research [4].

The most common plasma devices in biomedical applications employ dielectric barrier discharge (DBD) [5]. This type of discharge is characterized by an insulating layer between the electrodes, which prevents the direct flow of electric current, thus forming the so-called "dielectric barrier" [6]. Glass and silica are the commonly used materials for this barrier. However, ceramics, thin enamel coatings, aluminum oxide, and even polymers may also be employed in some instances [7–8]. Plasma is generated when a high-voltage potential is applied—typically in the kilovolt (kV) range—and can reach frequencies up to the megahertz (MHz) range, depending on the type and intended use of the equipment [9]. The device is usually positioned approximately 1 mm from the target tissue [6], facilitating efficient plasma generation at the desired location.

To ensure the effectiveness of APPJ in various applications, it is essential to adjust its operational parameters, such as power, to control the interaction between the plasma and the target correctly. In the case of biological tissues, improper handling of these parameters may lead to adverse effects, such as excessive thermal damage, which can result in undesirable skin changes like hypopigmentation or hyperpigmentation.

Given these characteristics of APPJ, this study aimed to evaluate the direct thermal effects generated by plasma contact with *ex vivo* biological samples using different device fulguration tips.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Plasma Jet Device

The plasma jet device used in this study was the Plasmax model, Fig. 1(a), manufactured by KLD Biosistemas. This is a portable atmospheric pressure plasma jet device that operates with alternating current (AC) and is equipped with two fulguration tips made of stainless steel: (a) a needle-holder type tip, Fig. 1(b), designed for fulguration using disposable acupuncture needles, and (b) a conical tip, Fig. 1(c), also used for fulguration, but with a slightly lower energy concentration compared to the needle tip.

Fig. 1 (a) Plasmax device (KLD) used in the experiments; (b) Needle-holder tip; (c) Conical tip

B. Ex Vivo Biological Tissue Samples

Due to its structural similarity to human skin, the selected *ex vivo* biological tissue sample was porcine abdominal skin. The tissue was cut into sections measuring approximately $4 \times 3 \text{ cm}^2$, with a thickness of 4.5 cm (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2 *Ex vivo* biological tissue sample from the porcine abdomen

The samples were obtained from commercial establishments and stored in a refrigerator at $5 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. During the tests, two samples (one for each type of tip) were taken to the laboratory and placed in a glass container.

C. Data Collection and Analysis Procedure

The plasma was applied continuously (in a single application, without repetitions) for seven minutes on both samples (one for each type of tip used). The plasma was

delivered at an approximate distance of 1 mm from the sample surface until the visible formation of the plasma plume. The plasma jet was then directed across the entire area of interest, without following a standardized movement pattern, ensuring full surface exposure to the plasma. Thermal images were acquired and recorded as MPEG Layer 4 (MP4) video files using an infrared camera, model FLIR T540 (Teledyne FLIR LLC), positioned 30 cm away from the samples at an approximate angle of 45 degrees.

After acquisition, the thermal image files were transferred to a personal computer and processed using custom software developed in MATLAB (MathWorks Inc.). Five random points were selected in the first frame (Fig. 3), and the application recorded the temperature at each point every 60 seconds. At the end of the process, a text file was generated containing the processed data, including minimum, average, and maximum temperatures for each of the five points.

The minimum, maximum, and average temperature metrics were selected due to their relevance in evaluating the direct thermal effects of plasma interaction with the samples. The maximum temperature indicates the thermal peak reached during the procedure, serving as a parameter to estimate the potential for thermal damage to the tissue. The average temperature represents a consolidated value over time, enabling comparisons between the fulguration tips and their respective heat distribution profiles.

Fig. 3 Points selected using the software

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The thermal analysis of the conical tip across the five measurement points (TP1 to TP5) showed a homogeneous temperature distribution on the samples. Figure 4(a) presents the average, minimum, and maximum temperature values during plasma application, allowing comparison between the obtained thermal parameters. Additionally, Figure 4(b) illustrates the temperature evolution over time, providing insight into the thermal dynamics generated by the tip.

When observing the average temperature, values ranged from $11.21 \pm 0.39 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ (TP4) to $13.34 \pm 0.82 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ (TP3), indicating slight thermal fluctuations during measurements,

without a clear trend of sustained increase or decrease. These results suggest a relatively stable behavior of the conical tip in the induced heating pattern.

The minimum temperatures recorded ranged from 10.32 °C (TP4) to 11.40 °C (TP3), while maximum values ranged from 11.61 °C (TP4) to 14.03 °C (TP3). In terms of dispersion, the highest standard deviation (0.82 °C) occurred at TP3, coinciding with the highest maximum temperature recorded (14.03 °C), which may indicate localized thermal instability.

Despite these variations, the standard deviation values remained low in all measurements, reinforcing the thermal consistency of the conical tip. This behavior may be attributed to its geometry, which, although promoting broader plasma dispersion, still delivers controlled thermal energy when applied at short distances across the sample surface.

Fig. 4 (a) Average, minimum, and maximum temperatures measured during plasma jet application on the porcine sample using the conical tip; (b) Temperature readings at the five measurement points (TP1 to TP5) during the test.

The thermal analysis of the needle holder tip was also conducted across the five measurement points (TP1 to TP5), with results shown in Figures 5(a) and 5(b).

The average temperatures remained relatively stable over time, ranging from 11.76 ± 0.22 °C (TP5) to 12.98 ± 0.40 °C (TP1 and TP2), indicating a uniform thermal distribution throughout the application. The low variation between times and consistently low standard deviations suggests more precise thermal control.

The minimum temperatures ranged from 11.33 °C (TP5) to 12.00 °C (TP1 and TP2), while maximum temperatures ranged from 11.98 °C (TP5) to 13.31 °C (TP1 and TP2), demonstrating a narrow and predictable thermal range. The highest maximum temperature observed was 13.31 °C, significantly lower than the peak recorded by the conical tip (14.03 °C).

The comparative analysis between the conical and needle holder tips showed significant differences in the thermal profiles generated during plasma application on porcine tissue. Both tips were subjected to the same experimental conditions, with manual application at close range and without a standardized movement sequence, suggesting that the observed variations are associated with the geometric characteristics of each tip.

Fig. 5 (a) Average, minimum, and maximum temperatures measured during plasma jet application on the porcine sample using the needle tip; (b) Temperature readings at the five measurement points (TP1 to TP5) during the test.

Previous studies indicate that modifications in electrode geometry, such as replacing pin-type electrodes or removing ring electrodes, significantly alter the electric field along the plasma plume, impacting its length and chemical reactivity. [10][11].

The conical tip showed a greater thermal amplitude, with average temperatures ranging from 11.21 ± 0.39 °C to 13.34 ± 0.82 °C and maximum values reaching 14.03 °C. The highest standard deviation (0.82 °C at TP3) indicates less control in heat distribution. This behavior may be related to tip geometry, resulting in greater surface thermal

variability. As highlighted by Zhang et al. [12], the tips' physical configuration, including the electrodes' positioning and shape, plays a crucial role in determining plasma discharge characteristics, such as temperature distribution and energy efficiency.

In contrast, the needle holder tip showed a more uniform thermal profile, with average temperatures between 11.76 ± 0.22 °C and 12.98 ± 0.40 °C and maximum values limited to 13.31 °C. Standard deviations were low and more consistent across all measured times, reflecting a more stable and predictable thermal delivery. This result may be attributed to the more focused geometry of the tip, which restricts the plasma dissipation area and favors greater concentration of thermal energy at the contact point.

As described by Walsh and Kong [13], a more intense and concentrated electric field along the plume favors the formation of longer and more reactive plasma plumes. Therefore, the absence of a sufficiently focused field in the conical tip may have contributed to a less uniform plume, reinforcing the hypothesis that its geometry induces a more diffuse electric field, resulting in greater surface thermal variability. Depending on the clinical goal, such characteristics can be advantageous or disadvantageous: for treatments requiring localized and controlled action, the needle holder tip may be more suitable. In contrast, the conical tip may be helpful in treating larger areas with less required precision.

Despite the consistent results observed, some methodological limitations must be considered when interpreting the findings. First, the use of only one sample per applicator tip restricts statistical analysis and does not allow for a comprehensive assessment of the reproducibility of the results. Furthermore, the use of ex vivo tissue, without blood perfusion, may lead to an overestimation of thermal retention compared to in vivo conditions, where blood flow acts as a heat sink. The initial cooling to 5 °C, although it standardized the experiments, may also have influenced the values recorded during the first moments of application. Finally, the surface moisture of the samples represents a relevant factor, as it can alter both thermal conductivity and the interaction of plasma with the tissue. Although a minimum level of standardization was maintained, minor variations cannot be completely ruled out.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

The needle holder tip showed more homogeneous thermal behavior, indicating greater control in heat distribution. On the other hand, the conical tip exhibited

greater thermal variability, with higher values, suggesting broader thermal dispersion.

These differences highlight that tip geometry directly influences the generated thermal profile, which may significantly impact plasma's clinical and therapeutic applications. Therefore, tip selection should be based on the need for thermal control and the specificity of the desired treatment.

Although the results were consistent, it is important to acknowledge the limitations of this study, particularly the use of ex vivo tissue without blood perfusion and the employment of only one sample per applicator tip, which restricts the generalization of the findings. Moreover, the influence of tissue surface moisture on thermal conduction cannot be completely ruled out.

Future studies are recommended to evaluate the thermal effects on living tissues and explore other variables such as application distance and different power settings to deepen the understanding of thermal mechanisms associated with plasma application.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors have no conflict of interest to declare.

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